

POSSIBILITIES OF SOCIAL AND SPIRITUAL SUPPORT FOR WOMEN AND IMPROVING LEGAL CULTURE

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Abstract: this article analyzes the improvement and strengthening of moral, political, social, legal, religious, spiritual and ideological relations between citizens in the process of the formation and development of civil society, the integration of education and upbringing in the process of social and spiritual support of women, the rise of their worldview .

Key words: gender equality, oppression, violence, social outlook, social mechanism, law, legal culture, socio-political activity, social protection, social stereotypes, family values.

INTRODUCTION

In the new Uzbekistan, social and spiritual support of women, the integration of education and upbringing in the development of their worldview, the improvement and strengthening of moral, political, social, legal, religious, spiritual and ideological relations between citizens in the process of the formation and development of civil society are important. After all, the relationship between the individual and the society has a strong influence on social development in today's globalization process. This is due to the fact that more young people, especially young girls, think independently, think freely, express their attitude to the surrounding events and events.

Domestic violence is physical, emotional, sexual, or financial abuse by a spouse or other intimate partner. Here are some of the common forms of domestic violence: Husband beating his wife, mentally humiliating her, insulting her offspring by blaming her family status or what her parents or relatives have done, sexually raping her wife, forcing her to satisfy her sexual needs through unnatural methods, or sexually humiliating her (insulting, humiliating, not having sex, walking with other women), limiting financially, not giving money, resisting a woman's study or work, etc.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In order to solve these situations and prevent them from such negative actions, legal socialization is definitely required from a woman. Socialization of women through participation in legal relations is an extremely complex process. Special phenomena such as legal awareness, legal thinking, knowledge, legal culture, upbringing, legal experience are manifested in this. In this process, it is natural that legal mentality and legal spirituality have a certain place. In the legal socialization of women, legal education and upbringing, promotion and campaigning, formation of legal culture, national values, customs, and traditions are of special importance. Based on the above considerations, we define the term legal socialization of women as follows: "Legal socialization of women is the process of women's exemplary behavior related to law in society, assimilation of social-legal norms, legal-spiritual mechanisms and legal values, and the process of following legal norms in the upbringing of children in the family." The assimilation of legal culture patterns, legal values and rules, legal

norms, principles by women leads to the formation of qualities that allow them to adapt to the current legal system and perform certain functions. In this case, they fulfill certain legal norms, rights and duties, adopt legal traditions and values. In this way, certain legal knowledge, experience, legal consciousness and culture are formed in them. That is, the legal socialization of women is the process of training them for the roles they should perform in the legal field [1].

Another important process in the legal socialization of women is the acquisition of legal values. It is known that "legal values are legal: norms, ideas, views, institutions, principles and events that are respected, appreciated by citizens and serve their interests in the regulation of social relations between people, society and the state" [2]. By mastering them, the subject achieves perfect legal socialization.

Another important process in the legal socialization of women is the acquisition of legal values. It is known that "legal values are legal: norms, ideas, views, institutions, principles and events that are respected, valued by citizens and serve their interests in the regulation of social relations between people, society and the state" [3]. By mastering them, the subject achieves perfect legal socialization.

Family education is always distinguished by its complexity and versatility, wonderful and beautiful. Each family is a unique world, a world within the world, at the same time, a world that does not fit into the world, it manifests its unique, unique characteristics in the work of education. That is why there are no one-size-fits-all guidelines for family education. Family is the primary social unit of society. It reflects the needs, interests, inclinations, upbringing and other types of social activities of family members. Systematic influence of parents on the basis of scientific worldview, spiritual-ethical, sophistication, labor and other social factors should remain the most urgent issue today.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In fact, the tasks of family legislation are to strengthen the family, build family relationships on the basis of mutual love, trust and respect, harmony, help each other, and the sense of responsibility of all its members to the family, prevent any person from arbitrarily interfering in family matters, is to ensure that its members exercise their rights without hindrance and that these rights are protected. But loopholes in the law or problems of improving the legislation on family preservation prevent the full fulfillment of this task. Family disputes are not only divorce, but also cases of paternity determination, alimony collection, child custody, property division between spouses, access to housing, finding that the right to use housing has been lost, and so on. meets.

By Decree No. PF-5938 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 18, 2020 "On measures to improve the socio-spiritual environment in society, further support the neighborhood institution and bring the system of work with family and women to a new level"[4] It was decided to carry out a unified state policy on strengthening the institution of the family, to provide targeted assistance to troubled and troubled families, and ultimately to organize work on the formation of a stable legal culture.

If we analyze the 7th chapter of the Constitution of our country regarding the rights of women, this chapter also gives a special place to the reproductive rights of women. Reproductive rights are one of the fundamental rights of every human being and include the rights to marry, have more children, and maintain reproductive health. The implementation of reproductive rights is based on the following principles:

- respect for human dignity;
- not allowing women to be discriminated against;
- the right to privacy;
- the right to personal freedom and personal security;
- the right to physical and mental health.

Today, the work carried out with women working in the fields of science and education in our country can be divided into two directions. After all, 72% of the employees working in this field are women.

The first direction is related to increasing the social and political activity of women working in educational institutions, and further improving the work of ensuring their active participation in the reforms implemented in our country, and this direction is considered one of the factors of the development of our country. can be done.

The second direction is work with girls studying in educational institutions, and this direction includes the following tasks:

a) establishing educational institution-family-neighborhood cooperation by strengthening the activities of parents' universities in local areas, increasing the activity of specialists in working with women in the neighborhoods;

b) to increase the activity of schoolgirls in educational institutions through "Kizlarjon" clubs and to meaningfully organize their free time by involving them in various circles;

c) increase students' legal knowledge, thereby forming their skills about their rights in marriage, marriage contract, couple and other family relations;

g) preparing young people for life in the appropriate class hours, paying special attention to the issues of life knowledge, occupation, readiness for family;

d) quality organization of services of psychologists in educational institutions, focusing on personnel, conducting psychological tests.

CONCLUSION

Targeted work is being done to expand the ranks of women scientists in our country, to support them in every way, and to bring the results of their research to the international level. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoev, in his Address to the Parliament in January 2020, acknowledged that the new idea of "Society is an initiator of reforms" is increasingly entering our daily activities, and that our nation is, in a certain sense, becoming a leader and initiator in creating its own future, as an executor and observer of reforms for many years. , recognized that we have already come to the level of strong focus on science.

According to 2019 statistics, the number of women in higher education also increased, and 40% of students were women, which is 36% more than in 2011. The literacy rate of women is 99.98%, which is one of the highest indicators in the world. However, according to the data, only 35% of women with secondary education are employed, and 68% of women with higher education are employed.

It is known that the expansion of higher education opportunities is an important factor in increasing the level of employment among women. Also, we should not stop calling for more women in politics and government, because it is not enough for women to get higher education, if a woman sets an example by being active in the intense processes, the desire of the country's girls to get education will increase.

In short, a legal framework has been created in Uzbekistan to prevent discrimination of women's rights and to attract women to active participation in the political, economic, social and cultural life of the country..

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